

MICROCAPSULE-BASED SELF-HEALING PROTECTIVE COATING USING LINSEED OIL HEALING AGENT

Dong-Min Kim, In-Ho Song, Ju-Young Choi, Seung-Won Jin, Kyeong-Nam Nam and Chan-Moon Chung*

Department of Chemistry, Yonsei University, 1 Yonseidae-gil Wonju, Gangwon-do 26493, Republic of Korea

* Corresponding author's E-mail : cmchung@yonsei.ac.kr

Abstract

A protective coating is used generally to protect substrate materials such as metals, ceramics and cementitious materials from environmental damage factors such as water, carbon dioxide and chloride ion. However, the coating can be damaged by thermal, photochemical, mechanical factors or etc. A self-healing protective coating can automatically repair the damage occurred in the coating. Thus the self-healing technique is utilized as a method to extend materials lifetime, improve public safety and reduce environmental pollution and maintenance cost. In this study, we have developed a microcapsule-type self-healing protective coating using linseed oil as healing agent for application to cementitious materials. Linseed oil undergoes an oxidative drying reaction upon exposure to oxygen: it turns into a soft film via radical polymerization of linoleic acid. The reaction conversion of C=C groups at room-temperature or low-temperature (-20°C) was measured by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). Linseed oil-loaded microcapsules were prepared by in-situ polymerization method using a urea-formaldehyde resin as a microcapsule wall material. Microcapsules were characterized by optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The microcapsules were mixed in a commercial coating formulation to prepare self-healing protective coating. The self-healing coating mixtures were applied on mortar specimens as cementitious materials to demonstrate self-healing properties. Healing properties of the self-healing protective coating were investigated by SEM, a water sorptivity test, the accelerated carbonation test and chloride ion penetration resistance test before and after scratching or cracking of the coating. Low-temperature self-healing was demonstrated with a saline solution sorptivity test conducted at -20°C. A healing efficiency was investigated through measurement of water or saline solution uptake.

Results and Discussion

FT-IR spectra of linseed oil reaction

Reaction conversion of linseed oil

Water uptake according to capsule content (scratch)

Linseed oil microcapsules

Water uptake according to temperature (scratch)

SEM image of scratched coating surfaces

Water uptake according to capsule content (crack)